

Print: 3082-4060
Online: 3082-4079

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

VOLUME 1

ISSUE 3 | JULY - SEPTEMBER ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue III | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

FROILAN T. YBAÑEZ, MAVE

Instructor III

Negros Oriental State University

froilan.ybanez@norsu.edu.ph

"WHISPERS FROM A MOTHER'S HEART"

In the quiet of dawn,
I stumbled upon a familiar box,
hidden beneath your half-a-century-old bed.
Dust-covered and timeworn,
it cradled silent treasures of our shared past:
letters, photographs,
and a faded lavender handkerchief—
the one you once painstakingly embroidered with my name.

Each item whispered stories
of your warmth, your laughter,
and most of all,
your unwavering love.

They brought back the memory
of one calloused yet gentle hand—
your hand—
smoothing my hair
as I sat on your lap,
just as an innocent child would.

Your soothing voice
echoed softly in my mind,
offering kind words of advice
to guide me through life's inevitable storms.

And then, as sunlight streamed in,
flooding my once dimly lit chamber,
I closed my eyes,
trying to grasp the depth and warmth of your embrace—
so tender,
I still feel it even now,
from afar and in a distant past.

Thank you, my dearest mother,
for a love that has endured through time
and remains a constant beam of light
forever glowing in my heart.

